

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MUTHURI****FIRST NAME: PAUL****PROGRAM CODE: DSSD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author applied: Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 11 Enterprise

List your seven key concepts with page number in the text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Writing a good academic paper (EUCLID 2021,7-12)
2. Some Rules of thumb for writing a paper (EUCLID 2021, 13)
3. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 34-37)
4. Style guide (EUCLID 2021,41-42)
5. American VS British (EUCLID 2021, 25-44)

BASICS OF ACADEMIC WRITING

1)INTRODUCTION

For some time, I have desired to obtain a Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.) Degree as the final level of my academic pursuit. But I had procrastinated on the decision for three years. This was due to fear of the unknown and resource constraints. But last year, I decided to search for a university offering a program that is affordable and will fit my working life. I finally settled on Ph.D. course in Sustainable Development and Diplomacy.

After settling on the university and course to undertake, the next stage was registering with EUCLID University and paying the fees. This was followed by processing the university's registration and login details. I had initial challenges getting login passwords for CMS and LMS, which were later sorted out by the admission team. This allowed me to access course materials for the first unit, International Academic Writing (ACA-401/ACA-401D).

I have gone through the course park for International Academic Writing (ACA-401/ACA-401D) course period one, which gives an overview of writing a good academic essay. The course covers seven main areas: writing good academic essays, punctuation, American vs. British English, rules of thumb, plagiarism, writing style guide, CMS CRIB

Sheet, Latin Abbreviations and expressions, and sample corrections to papers. I have also gone through a tutorial video by Professor Laurent Cleenewerck and a YouTube video on Grammarly writing and using Zotero. I have learned that academic writing is more focused and detailed, requiring attention to details such as commas and punctuation.

According to EUCLID (2021, 25-33), a writer should guard against PLAGIARISM and follow a specific STYLE OF WRITING GUIDE. I have learned how to avoid plagiarism when writing an academic paper. I have further noted that EUCLID University recommends using Chicago Rules (Turabian), which I will use to write my academic papers.

In this response paper, I will discuss five significant areas covered by the course pack ACA-401/ACA-401D period one and tutorial videos. These include writing a good academic paper, rules of thumb, plagiarism, style guide, and the American version versus the British version of English.

2) WRITING A GOOD ACADEMIC ESSAY

The first chapter of the course provides the basic steps for writing an academic essay EUCLID (2021, 7). A key requirement of writing a good academic paper is for the writer to start writing early. This entails defining the topic question, analyzing the basics and drafting the initial plan. An early start gives the writer enough time to read, research the topic, think, and write. Further, defining topic questions requires one to write everything known about the topic and analyze and present the answer. Developing an initial plan requires developing thoughts and ideas about the research topic, which involves creating a preliminary essay plan to guide the research. Through the video, Professor Cleenewerck and Dr. Gulma highlight that “When planning to write a paper, one should have enough time to read, research the topic well, think and write.”

As a student of academic writing, I agree with the author that preparing and planning early when writing an academic essay is critical. This will help me save time and resources by focusing on the writing area.

According to EUCLID (2021, 9), the next step in writing is to read and research the topic to be written. It is essential to make notes when reading as this will form the basis for essay writing. It is recommended to underline or highlight relevant information that will be revisited for reading, while keeping in mind the topic of the essay and ensuring sound evidence is produced to support the argument.

According to EUCLID (2021, 9), essay writing requires the writer to have both creative and critical thinking. Critical thinking enables the writer to focus on the idea. The writer should also ensure that the essay is balanced with various information and viewpoints from different authors. Further, good essay writing requires organizing ideas and drawing a plan, including possible answer questions, selecting information, and reviewing notes.

In addition, writing a good essay requires producing a first draft that is well-aligned. The last step in essay writing is the submission of the essay for marking. Still, before submission, one should ensure that the essay is written according to the course guidelines provided with the structure and framework of the essay. EUCLID (2021, 10). The structure of the essay should include an introduction, body, and conclusion. The introduction involves introducing the topic areas, answering the thesis questions, and providing a brief essay roadmap. The body comprises a paragraph that answers the essay's question through discussions. Conclusion entails restating the answer to the question and re-summarizing the main points.

EUCLID (2021, 11) states that a good essay should have references. References will guide against plagiarism, which is a serious academic offense. An essay should use the referenced style recommended by the faculty or school.

The last step in essay writing is submitting the essay for marking, but before handing over the essay, the essay must be edited. Editing involves checking the structure of the essay and revising sentences. It is also essential to ensure the essay conforms to the requirements of the course outline.

3) RULES OF THUMB OF WRITING

According to EUCLID (2021, 12), academic writing has some rules to guide writing. First, state the main thesis of your paper at the beginning of the essay and, if possible, in the opening paragraph. Each paragraph should have a main point that relates to the argument the writer is writing on. This makes follow of ideas for the reader to understand.

Paragraphs for the essay should be arranged in a logical and sequential flow—punctuation and spelling using a good dictionary. There is a need to provide transition signals that will enable a reader to follow the sequence of ideas from sentence to sentence and paragraph. There is a need to ensure that arguments in an essay make sense and are well-balanced. The evidence in the essay needs to be relevant and supported by argument.

The writer should use a consistent citation style, which is referenced with quotes in academic writing. Where guided, it is essential to follow special instructions or guidelines for the assignment and remain within the set word limit. This will ensure the writer remains within the expected boundaries of the essay.

In writing an academic essay, writing short sentences and avoiding page-long paragraphs is recommended. Where a sentence occupies more than five lines, there is a need to divide the sentence. If a paragraph goes for more than 20 lines, it should be divided into another paragraph to enable follow-up of information.

To support the assertions in essay writing, the writer must attribute views to the person whose ideas are addressed and indicate the evidence for the attribution by noting

relevant passages. This includes quotations where necessary. A passage should be quoted only if the passage plays an essential role in the paper.

Plagiarism is a key concern in academic writing. Plagiarism occurs when you use the words of a source without quotation marks. You should not present a close paraphrase from a source: use the exact words with quotation marks or restate the point in your own words. Secondly, plagiarism occurs when you take ideas from a source without footnoting the source. Sanctions for plagiarism depend on its severity and may range from lower grades on an assignment to a failing grade for the course.

Before submitting the essay, it is essential to ensure the essay is formatted correctly. Double-line spacing readable font (at least size 12), application of number pages, and setting wide margins are recommended. The writer must know the date the assignment is due. Submitting a late assignment will attract a penalty. The writer should also know where and the person the assignment is being submitted.

4) AMERICAN VERSUS BRITISH ENGLISH

According to EUCLID (2021, 24-30), two main types of languages are used in writing: the American and English versions. Various factors are responsible for the difference between British and American English being witnessed. These include the size of the population in the UK and the US, the influence of the free market economy in the US versus the UK, the magnitude of higher education in the United States of America versus the United Kingdom, and the magnitude of publishing in the US versus that of the UK. Professor Laurent Cleenewerck states, “American and British English are variants of World English. As such, they are more similar than different”.

Kenya, a former British colony, has adopted the UK English version, which is used in schools and public places. I have used the UK English version in all my school life. However, since the EUCLID university requirement is to use the American English version, I will strive to learn and apply the same in all my academic writings.

Further, most language divergence is attributed to differing national histories and cultural development. As it is, there are general categories of difference between Standard American English (SAE) and Standard British English (SBE), and each has its Socialistic value, for instance, Different Pronunciation, Although the exact spelling, for example, Advertisement (advert), Controversy, Laboratory, Secretary, Leisure, Renaissance, Migratory, Clerk. On the other hand, there are also different spellings, Although they have the same Pronunciation, for example, Axe – Ax, Plough - Plow, Colour – Color, Cheque – Check, and also there can be the Same term, Different but Similar spelling, and pronunciation for example Aluminium – Aluminum, Polythene – Polyethylene variation in terminology, Maths – Math. There are also regional Variations, Identities, and stereotypes because of variations in terminology.

5) PLAGIARISM

According to EUCLID (2021, 33-37), plagiarism occurs when the writer uses a source of information without acknowledging the author of that source of information. It's essential when using quotes, paraphrases, statistical data, or visuals, such as graphs borrowed from another source; credit should always be given to the author. Plagiarism is a serious academic offense that can have serious consequences. To avoid such crimes, a writer must always cite the author or the source that has provided the information.

On the other hand, quotations can be used sparingly, or else it makes the work look like it is not your own. Instead of overusing quotations, one can use paraphrasing. However, the paraphrase must be different from the author's original wording, and the information must remain the same as the author's.

6) STYLE GUIDE

According to EUCLID (2021, 41-42), a style guide documents writers' approaches to certain elements that need to be consistent. EUCLID University recommends using the Chicago Rules (Turabian Manual) writing style. However, it also accepts other internationally recognized Rules. The University also recommends using the American English version but allows the use of British English so long as the writer does not mix both writing styles.

A style guide is essential as it makes the final publication coherent and consistent. Style guides also provide a means of documenting basic rules or features of your writing, which ensures consistency in the written output. Style encompasses many aspects of the writing, such as preferred sentence length, manuscript layout, font usage, depth of treatment of the subject, spelling, use of abbreviations, symbols, paragraph numbering, and indentation. A style guide is an invaluable tool for any writer.

7) CONCLUSION

International Academic Writing is my first unit/Subject to be studied under Ph.D. program in Sustainable Development and Diplomacy (DSSD). Period one of the units has introduced me to academic writing and, more so, the use of basic language skills. This includes punctuation, plagiarism, different styles of writing, and American vs UK languages. I found the session initially challenging since I had taken a long time before rejoining pursuing studies. I have learned that basic language skills matter a lot in writing; therefore, a writer must be detailed and specific in all aspects.

The course materials covered included a course pack period one and tutorial videos. The course has helped me to understand different academic writing styles. These include the Chicago Manual of Styles (CMS) and the Turabian Manual for Writers, which is used at EUCLID University.

I have also learned that there is a difference between the US and UK English languages in terms of spelling, punctuation, and pronunciation. I have noted that in writing, it is essential to follow one English version without mixing the two. Similarly, emphasis has been laid on the importance of following a specific style guide while writing a scientific paper. In other words, one must follow some rules of the thumb when writing a scientific paper.

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